

Article Arrival Date

24.09.2022

Article Published Date

20.12.2022

THE EFFECT OF SUPERHERO CARTOONS ON SELF-CONFIDENCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS**Halil Dündar CANGÜVEN**Sorumlu Yazar, Hadiye Kuradacı BİLSEM, ORCID: [orcid.org/ 0000-0002-7931-9449](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7931-9449)**Begüm Ahsen KAYA**Hadiye Kuradacı BİLSEM, ORCID: [orcid.org/ 0000-0001-6271-0065](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6271-0065)**Ahmet TAKAN**Hadiye Kuradacı BİLSEM, ORCID: [orcid.org/ 0000-0003-3854-2000](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3854-2000)**Abstract**

The aim of this study is to determine the effect of superhero cartoons on self-confidence in primary school students. The sample of the research consists of 8 students who attend primary school in the 2020-2021 academic year, determined by purposeful sampling. Participants are between the ages of 8-10. Interview technique, one of the qualitative research methods, was used in the research. The opinions of the participants were taken with a semi-structured interview form by taking expert opinions. After the expert's opinion, 8 open-ended interview questions and demographic features were included in the form. Researchers independently coded the interview records and then common codes were determined. The codes were reanalyzed and categories were created. For the validity and reliability of the research, besides the volunteering of the participants, direct quotations were made under the table and shared with other researchers. The reliability of the study was calculated as 85%. The codes created by the participants with their definitions of self-confidence, "Confidence in oneself, not afraid of anything and not being ashamed", the codes they created about watching cartoons and their reasons for choosing "Adventure and Action", the codes they created about wanting to be like a superhero in a cartoon "yes". The codes they created for being self-confident like those superheroes in real life were determined as "flying, solving problems and helping people". 4 categories in the first, third and fourth sub-problems; 5 categories in the fifth, seventh and eighth sub-problems; and 6 categories were determined in the second and sixth sub-problems. The fact that children's virtual and TV watching is under family control is of great importance in terms of their personal development. Individuals' monitoring should be in line with family, community and value judgments. In addition, the content of individuals' monitoring should be supported by moral value judgments.

Words: Values, Primary school students, superhero, cartoon, self-confidence

¹² Hadiye Kuradacı BİLSEM, suna_kaya_61@hotmail.com, ORCID: [orcid.org/ 0000-0001-6271-0065](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6271-0065)³ Hadiye Kuradacı BİLSEM, ahmettakan@hotmail.com, ORCID: [orcid.org/ 0000-0003-3854-2000](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3854-2000)

1. Introduction

Self-confidence is the feeling of trusting oneself. There are many situations that affect self-esteem. Events such as humiliation, exclusion, and mockery affect children greatly. They may find themselves flawed in society or view themselves through the eyes of others. This negatively affects their self-esteem. In addition, superhero cartoons also affect children's self-confidence.

Cartoons are created by rapid succession of pictures, suggesting things are moving. Especially superhero cartoons are loved and watched by children all over the world. Superheroes are people who are superior to normal people. Their aim is to promote the well-being of society. One of the reasons for the formation of superheroes is superhero cartoons. These cartoons have effects especially on young children. Kids often want to be like them after watching superhero cartoons. It is quite easy for young children to believe what happens in fairy tales, cartoons, etc. In addition to this, they also want to feel like the characters (superheroes) there and want to be like them. An important factor in young children's love for them is that superheroes have extraordinary powers.

Superhero cartoons have positive or negative effects. For example, after watching superhero cartoons, children may think that they can change the world. They may assume that they are superheroes and display various behaviors, perhaps risking their lives. However, it also has positive aspects. When they feel like superheroes, they can feel more confident or brave and become more successful individuals in daily life.

Mass media has become an inseparable part of our daily routine, especially in the age of technology. People who turn to these devices to do various activities such as following the current news, acquiring new information, having fun, and using their spare time in a useful way are faced with the effect of television-centered messages intensively (Doğan & Göker, 2012).

Television plays an important role in most children's lives. If we look at the reasons why children watch TV, it is understood that adults differ in the reasons for watching TV. While most adults watch television to spend their free time, children watch television, which they find entertaining, in order to understand what is going on in the world. According to some of the data obtained, almost all of the houses have televisions (Öztürk & Karayağız, 2007).

Children, who are the future of society, are very much affected by television, which is an effective mass communication tool by constantly renewing itself. Because televisions can be both visual and auditory and in some aspects educational and entertaining (Çilenti, 1984). Television, which is one of the mass media, includes advertisements, serials, competitions, documentaries, sports programs, etc., and cartoons that children love, which can easily attract children's attention thanks to their colorful and animated visuals, and whose number increases rapidly. Television can affect people's thoughts directly or indirectly (Yetim & Sarıçam, 2016).

In addition to the fact that there are events such as hitting, wounding, crushing, shooting, bombing, using blast-cutting tools, fighting in order to make children laugh, draw attention and entertain children in cartoon programs, there are positive and negative events reflected with an atmosphere supported by colors, symbols, shapes, figures and signs. Negative behaviors can be done by children (Akçalı, 2007).

In studies on the relationship between television and children, the negative effects of television on children were mostly investigated (Altınış & Altun, 2021). In addition to TV programs with negative content, some cartoon programs are published in the International Journal of Social Studies, instilling the feeling of socialization, empathy, sharing, helping the child, accelerating the child's cognitive development process, developing early, effective and quick learning in the child, making the child discover different things, accelerating the child's language development. states that it contributes to the development of the child, such as (Önder & Doğal, 2006).

It is quite easy for young children to believe what happens in fairy tales, cartoons, etc. In addition to this, they also want to feel like the characters (superheroes) there and want to be like them. An important factor in young children's love for them is that superheroes have extraordinary powers.

Atalay, Nural, and Ada (2021), in their study titled Teachers' Opinions on the effect of theater on the prevention of undesirable behaviors in preschool children, stated that preschool teachers reduce and some of them eliminate undesirable behaviors in students. In addition, the students who participated in the theater activity stated that they voluntarily gave up the computer, internet and cartoons and preferred the theater instead.

Altınış and Altun (2021) examined the Pırl cartoon, which was broadcast on TRT Kids (TRT Çocuk), in terms of values education. In the research, a total of 15 values were determined, including responsibility, advice, benevolence, aesthetics, friendship, kindness, desire to know and understand, trust, self-confidence, generosity, consolation, tolerance, honesty, love and regret.

Yener, Yılmaz and Sen (2021). In their study called Value Education in Cartoons: TRT Kids Example, they stated that while the values of cooperation and solidarity were mostly discussed, the value of empathy was not included. In addition, they stated that sufficient and appropriate number of values were included in the cartoon durations.

When the literature studies are examined, no study has been found that examines the self-confidence of children and their relationship with the cartoons they watch. In this respect, it is thought that the research will add a different perspective to the literature.

Aim

The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of superhero cartoons on self-confidence in primary school students. In accordance with the purpose, the main problem of the research is how does superhero cartoons affect the self-confidence of primary school students? The sub-problems of the research are:

1. How do participants define self-confidence?
2. What are the participants' types of watching cartoons and the reasons for their preference?
3. Did the participants want to be like the superhero in the cartoon?
4. What would it be like if the participants were as self-confident as those heroes in real life? What would they do?
5. How do the participants evaluate the self-confidence or courage of the superheroes?
6. Do the participants think that cartoons are suitable for real life?

7. Do the families of the participants interfere with the cartoons they watch?
8. What do the families of the participants think about the cartoons they watch?

2. Method

In this section, the model of the research, the sample of the research, data collection tools, data analysis and validity-reliability are included.

Interviews were conducted with the volunteers participating in this study outside of school hours. Before the interviews, the families and the participants were informed, the written consent of the parents was obtained, and the participants were made to volunteer. During all interviews, families were with the participants.

Sample of the Research

This study was carried out with 8 primary school students in the 2020-2021 academic year. Participants are between the ages of 8-10. Inclusion criteria for the study: It was determined that the participants were primary school students, the participants watched television, and the participants had knowledge about superheroes.

Data collection tool

Literature review and collection of basic information : Through the literature review, interview techniques and questions in previous studies were examined.

Creating the first draft of the semi-structured interview form: The first draft of the semi-structured interview form was created by the researchers by using the information obtained. The form includes 8 open-ended interview questions and questions with demographic characteristics.

Receiving expert opinions about the semi-structured interview form: The study was requested to gain academic value by checking the form, identifying and minimizing errors, and the criticisms and recommendations received were taken into account. In this section, we worked with three independent academic experts.

Finalizing the semi-structured interview form according to expert opinions: After the experts' opinions were evaluated, final additions were made to the semi-structured interview form and it was prepared. After the expert opinion, 8 open-ended interview questions and demographic characteristics were included in the form.

Determination of the participants: While choosing the participants, the selection of the participants who can find answers according to the purpose was taken into consideration.

Conducting the interview: The interview was conducted over a virtual environment. The interviews lasted approximately 15-20 minutes. Audio recorded with the permission of the participants.

Analysis of Data - Validity and Reliability

In the analysis of the data, the researchers involved in the study made independent coding and came to a common decision.

The reliability of the study was calculated with the formula of Consensus / (Agreement + Disagreement) x 100 (Miles & Huberman, 1994) and the reliability was calculated as 85%. According to Yıldırım and Şimşek (2013), if the reliability value is 70%, it is sufficient for the study to be considered reliable.

3. Findings

The data obtained in the study are given in tables in this section.

Table.1. Codes of the first sub-problem

	S.1.	S.2.	S.3.	S.4.	S.5.	S.6.	S.7.	S.8.	Total
trust yourself	x	-	x	-	-	-	-	x	3
be able to express their thoughts	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
not be afraid of anything	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
to introduce yourself	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	1
not be ashamed	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	1
make yourself proud	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	1
not knowing	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	1
using my courage	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	1
Total									10

54

Table 1 shows the codes created by the participants regarding their definitions of self-confidence. S1, S3, and S8 participants shared the "self-confidence" code.

Table.2. Category of the first sub-problem

	f	%
Self confidence	4	40.00%
idea	2	20.00%
bravery	2	20.00%
to be proud	2	20.00%
Total	10	100.00%

The categories created by the participants according to the first sub-problem are given in Table 2. The most preferred category by the participants is "self-confidence" with a rate of 40.00% .

Table.3. Codes for the second sub-problem

	S.1.	S.2.	S.3.	S.4.	S.5.	S.6.	S.7.	S.8.	Total
adventure	x	x	x	x	-	-	-	-	4
action	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
fight	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
romantic	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
comedy	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
animation	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	1
enjoy	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	1
suitable to age	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	1
don't be silly	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	1
not watching	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	1
cartoon	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
to watch	x	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	2
to watch	-	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	2
not watching	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	1
Total									14

When we look at Table 3, it is seen that the codes created by the participants regarding the types of watching cartoons and the reasons for their preference. The common codes of the participants were determined as "adventure and action". Other codes were specified by only one participant.

55

Table.4. Categories of the second sub-problem

	f	%
happiness	3	15.00%
watching	4	20.00%
excitement	7	35.00%
emotional	2	10.00%
cartoons	2	10.00%
negative thoughts	2	10.00%
Total	20	100.00%

In Table 4, the categories preferred by the participants for the second sub-problem are given. The category most preferred by the participants is "excitement" with a rate of 35.00%. Then "watching" became the most created category with 20.00%.

Table.5. Codes of the third sub-problem

	S.1.	S.2.	S.3.	S.4.	S.5.	S.6.	S.7.	S.8.	Total
yes	x	x	-	-	x	-	-	x	4
not wanting	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	1
loving them	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
wanting when you're young	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	1
wanting too much	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	1
wanting to fly	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	x	2
ask for a little	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	1
no	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	1
to be beautiful	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
request	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Total									10

Table 5 shows the codes that the participants created with their wish to be like the superhero in the cartoon. It was observed that the participants of S1, S2 and S5 formed the common code of "yes". The "wanting to fly" code was determined by two participants. Other codes were determined by only one participant.

Table.6. Categories of the third sub-problem

	f	%
positive thinking	4	28.57%
nice feeling	3	21.43%
negative thinking	2	14.29%
wanting	5	35.71%
Total	14	100.00%

56

Considering the categories preferred by the participants for the third sub-problem, it is given in table 8 that the most created category is "wanting" with 35.71% , and then "positive thinking" with 28.57% .

Table.7. Codes of the fourth sub-problem

	S.1.	D.2.	D.3.	S.4.	D.5.	D.6.	D.7.	D.8.	Total
helping people	x	x	x	-	x	-	-	-	4
fly	-	x	-	x	-	-	-	-	2
to solve problems	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	1
to be invisible	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	1
not helping people	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	1
protect from evil	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	1
not to be real	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	1
save people	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	1
helping the elderly	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	1
save themselves	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	1

i don't care	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	1
Total									15

In Table 7, the codes that the participants created with their self-confidence status like those heroes in real life are given. It was observed that the participants of S1, S2, S3 and S5 formed the common code of "helping people", and the participants of S2 and S4 formed the common code of "fly". The remaining codes were determined by only one participant.

Table.8. Categories of the fourth sub-problem

	f	%
to cooperate	7	46.67%
to save	3	20.00%
negative	1	6.67%
imaginatiom	4	26.67%
Total	15	100.00%

In Table 8, the categories created by the participants for the fourth sub-problem are given. The most preferred category was “ to cooperate ” with 46.67% . The second preferred category was the expression “imagination” with a rate of 26.67%.

Table.9. Codes for the fifth sub-problem

	S.1.	S.2.	S.3.	S.4.	S.5.	S.6.	S.7.	S.8.	Total
enjoyable	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
interesting	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
uselessness	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	1
to be fearless	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	1
being good with their self-confidence	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
beautiful	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	1
be in vain self-confidence	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	1
protect people	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	1
no	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	1
not to be real	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	1
absurd	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	1
good	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	1
Total									12

In Table 9, the codes created by the participants with the self-confidence and courage of the superheroes are given. It was determined that the participants did not create a common code.

Table.10. Categories belonging to the fifth sub-problem

	f	%
fun	2	16.67%
negativity	4	33.33%
confidence	2	16.67%
bravery	2	16.67%

positive	2	16.67%
Total	12	100.00%

Considering the categories preferred by the participants for the fifth sub-problem, the rate of the expression "negativity", which is the most preferred category, is seen as 33.33%.

Table.11. Codes of the sixth sub-problem

	S.1.	S.2.	S.3.	S.4.	S.5.	S.6.	S.7.	S.8.	Total
injustice	x	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	2
psychological disorders	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
upset	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
no	x	-	x	-	-	x	x	-	4
injustice	x	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	2
do nothing	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	1
not suitable	-	-	x	x	-	-	-	x	3
yes	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	1
fits	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	1
not to be real	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	1
partly suitable	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	1
not exist	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Total									19

When we look at the codes created by the participants in Table 11 with the suitability of the cartoons to real life, it is seen that there is no common code, but the "no" common code of S1, S3, S6 and S7 participants, and the "not suitable" common code of S3, S4 and S8 participants.

58

Table.12. Categories of the sixth sub-problem

	f	%
injustice	4	21.05%
to be fit	3	15.79%
not appropriate	3	15.79%
psychological	2	10.53%
reality	2	10.53%
negativity	5	26.32%
Total	19	100.00%

Looking at the table 12, which includes the categories of the sixth sub-problem, the category most created by the participants was "negativity" with a rate of 26.32%. Then, the expression "injustice" took place with a rate of 21.05%.

Table.13 . Codes of the seventh sub-problem

	S.1.	S.2.	S.3.	S.4.	S.5.	S.6.	S.7.	S.8.	Total
yes	x	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	2
allow	-	x	-	x	-	-	-	-	2
not suitable for children	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
to be harmful	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	1
not interfere if appropriate	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	x	1
get angry if not appropriate	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	1
little	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	1
a little	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	1
fear	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	1
filthy beast	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	1
to be at war	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	1
Total									13

Table 13 shows the codes created by the participants' families when they intervened in the cartoons they watched. While the participants did not create a common code, the "yes" code for S1 and S3 participants, the "allow" code for S2 and S4 participants, and the "not interfere if appropriate" code for S5 and S8 participants were determined.

Table.14. Categories of the seventh sub-problem

Themes		f	%
desire		4	30.77%
not appropriate		2	15.38%
positive thinking		1	7.69%
negative emotion		4	30.77%
time		2	15.38%
Total		13	100.00%

When we look at the categories of the seventh sub-problem in Table 14, the most preferred codes were the expressions "desire" and "negative emotion" with a rate of 30.77%.

Table.15.The codes of the eighth sub-problem

	S.1.	S.2.	S.3.	S.4.	S.5.	S.6.	S.7.	S.8.	Total
thinking it will hurt	x	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	2
thinking that you be afraid	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
to say nothing	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	1
thinking it's not helpful	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	1
say do whatever you want	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	1
not wanting to watch	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
to say nothing for good ones	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	1
watch with families	-	-	-	-	x	x	-	-	2
get angry if bad	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	x	2

find suitable for age	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	1
to love	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	1
Total								14

The codes created by the participants' thoughts about the cartoons they watched are given above. The common code “thinking it will hurt” was determined for S1 and S3 participants.

Table.16. Categories of the eighth sub-problem

		f	%
categories	harmful	5	35.71%
	not interfere	2	14.29%
	family permit	3	21.43%
	negative emotion	2	14.29%
	suitable	2	14.29%
	Total	14	100.00%

participants for the eighth sub-problem are given in Table 16. The rate of the expression “harmful”, which is the most preferred category by the participants, is 35.71% .

4. Discussion and Conclusion

When the categories created by the participants regarding the definitions of self-confidence were examined, it was seen that they stated the expressions of Self-Confidence, Thought, Courage, and Pride. This situation can be evaluated as the participants have a deep thought about self-confidence. In addition, it can be thought that the cartoons watched encourage them and this situation makes them proud. According to Eldeleklioğlu (2004), self-confidence is the determinant of behaviors, having positive judgments about oneself, loving himself, thinking that he is sufficient, realizing that he is valuable, being at peace with himself, accepting himself as he is and knowing himself. According to Karataş (2017), it is to love oneself, to think that he is sufficient in his wishes and to accept himself as he is. This shows that the self-confidence definitions of the participants overlap with the definitions in the literature.

Happiness, Watching, Excitement, Emotional, Cartoons, Negative thoughts were included in the categories created by the participants regarding the types of watching cartoons and the reasons for their preference. It can be considered that the participants watched the cartoons with a great sense of excitement. In addition, it was observed that some participants sometimes had negative thoughts while watching cartoons. According to Kernan (2007), every game played in early childhood has different types such as exploration game, constructive play, creative play, dramatic play, psychomotor play, language and word play. This situation shows that the participants' types of watching cartoons and the reasons for their preference match with their definitions in the literature. According to Doğan and Göker (2012), television watching habits can cause addiction in children, as in every part of today's society. According to Rideout, Vandewater and Wartella (2003); Almost all preschool children watch television, and it has been observed that children between the ages of 4 and 6 watch television for approximately 2 hours a day.

When the categories created by the participants about wanting to be like the superhero in the cartoon were examined, it was noticed that they formed the expressions Positive thinking, Good feeling, Negative thought, Not wanting. This situation can be evaluated as the participants want to look like superheroes and as a result of this watching event, they have positive feelings. According to Berk (2013), beings that can do extraordinary things such as unreal beings may

have dreams that they can affect the world with their dreams. According to Akçalı 2007, cartoons include events such as hitting, wounding, crushing, shooting, bombing, using blast-cutting tools, fighting, as well as using colors, symbols, symbols, shapes, figures and signs to make them laugh, draw attention or entertain children. Positive and/or negative behaviors reflected in a supported world can be practiced by children. Children can take cartoon characters as models as well as taking their teacher, their older sister or older brother, their mother and father as an example. In this case, it is seen that the participants' desire to be like the superhero in the cartoon and the definitions in the literature are identified.

Helping, rescuing, negative and imaginary categories were created regarding the participants' self-confidence like those heroes in real life. This situation can be interpreted as the participants are aware that they help people like those heroes and that they are imaginary characters. According to a study in the Journal of Early Childhood Studies (2020), children stated that 43.5% used the characteristics of superheroes for positive purposes, while 15.5% stated that they used them for negative purposes. In 41%, it was determined that the purpose of use was neutral. According to Aydın (2018), the reason why children are more affected by the broadcasts they watch on television is the learning process of childhood. Children demonstrate most of the information they learn by imitating what they see. This shows that the self-confidence of the participants in real life, like those heroes, and the definitions in the literature match.

The categories created by the participants regarding the self-confidence and courage of the superheroes were determined as Fun, Negativity, Self-Confidence, Courage, and Positive. Although the participants thought negatively about this issue, it was seen that they enjoyed watching these heroes and thought that they were a source of courage. According to a study by Karaca (2011), when the pictures used in cartoons are compared with the drawings of children, it is seen that children's self-confidence can be negatively affected. Tokdemir, Deveci, Açık, Yağmur, Gülbayrak, and Türkoğlu (2009) stated in a study they conducted that primary school students who watch broadcasts with a high content of violence resort to violence at a high rate and use violence as a solution to problems. This shows that the self-confidence and courage of the participants' superheroes and the definitions in the literature overlap. For this reason, it has been determined that primary school students are mostly not aware of the negative effects of cartoon programs.

When the categories created by the participants about the suitability of cartoons for real life were examined, it was seen that the expressions of Injustice, Being Appropriate, Not Suitable, Psychological, Reality, Negativity were formed. The participants observed that the cartoons were built on injustice. This situation can be evaluated as the constructs arouse negative thoughts in the participants. According to Güven and Akıncı (2014), since the heroes in cartoons are animals, humans and imaginary beings, it is not possible to associate them with real life. This shows that the self-confidence and courage of the participants' superheroes and the definitions in the literature match.

It was determined that the categories created by the participants' families about intervening in the cartoons they watched were Desire, Unsuitable, Positive thinking, Negative emotion, and Time. This situation was evaluated as that the families of the participants mostly had negative feelings, but the participants followed it persistently. In addition, families think that it is not appropriate and intervene from time to time. It is seen that families do not have much positive feelings towards the cartoons that children watch. According to Yetim and Sarıçam, (2016) Yaşar

Ekici, (2015), in addition to the fact that parents are a model for children with their own program selection and way of watching, the duration of children's watching cartoons, the selection of cartoons to be watched in accordance with the age and developmental characteristics of children, and the selection of cartoons They should be watched under the control of their parents. According to Samur, Demirhan, Soydan, and Önkol (2014), the simplest thing to do so that the harmful programs that parents watch on their children do not affect them is to not watch the programs that are concerned about the content. This situation shows that the definitions in the literature overlap with the intervention of the families of the participants in the cartoons they watch.

The categories created by the participants about the thoughts of their families about the cartoons they watched were Harmful, Not to interfere, Family leave, Negative emotion, Being appropriate. It was observed that the families of the participants mostly thought that superhero cartoons were harmful. However, some families allow and do not interfere properly. According to a study of Darga, Zayimoğlu Öztürk and Öztürk (2021); When the views of the participants' parents were examined, the majority of the parents said that their children were influenced by cartoons and practiced the behaviors they saw, and it was determined that these behaviors included negative behaviors such as using slang words, displaying aggressive behaviors, and being too insistent. According to Ravikiran, Baliga, Jain, and Kotian (2014), they stated that parents should be made aware of the harmful aspects of cartoons, so that children are not affected by their beneficial aspects. This situation shows that the opinions of the participants' families about the cartoons they watch and the definitions in the literature.

5. Suggestions

Cartoons and other movies greatly influence individuals' personalities and lifestyles. This effect is greater in individuals who have not completed their personality development. The simplest thing to do is family control to prevent harmful programs they watch do not affect them (Demirhan, Soydan, & Önkol, 2014). This situation;

- Individuals should be directed to follow-ups that will positively affect their self-confidence.
- Individuals' watchings should be in a way that gives them positive emotions.
- Individuals' desire to be like superheroes should not lead them to negative behaviors.
- The cartoons that individuals watch should be in a way that will increase their willingness to engage in positive behavior.
- Individuals should know that cartoons are not suitable for real life.
- Monitoring of individuals should be under family control.
- The content of individuals' monitoring should be supported by moral value judgments.

Suggestions are presented in the form.

Resources

Akçalı, O. G. (2007). Müzik öğretmenlerinin eğitim müziğinde çoksesli eşliklemeye yaklaşımları ve eşlikte harf şifre yöntemini kullanma durumları (Master's thesis, Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü).

Alabay, E. (2020). "Kahramanın Kim?": Okul öncesi dönem çocuklarının kahramanlarının incelenmesi. *Erken Çocukluk Çalışmaları Dergisi*, 4(1), 152-171.

Altmış, Z. G., & Altun, M. (2021). "Pırl" Çizgi Filminin Değerler Eğitimi Açısından Değerlendirilmesi. *OPUS Uluslararası Toplum Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 17(38), 5382-5411.

- Atalay, A., Nural, E., & Ada, Ş.(2021). Okul Öncesi Çocuklarda Görülen İstenmeyen Davranışların Önlenmesinde Tiyatronun Etkisine İlişkin Öğretmen Görüşleri. *Ulusal Eğitim Akademisi Dergisi*, 5(2), 223-238.
- Berk, L. E. (2013). *Bebekler ve çocuklar. N. Işıkoğlu, Çev.) Ankara: Nobel.*
- Coşkunçay, F. H. (2019). İlkokul 3. Ve 4. sınıf öğrencilerinin Ders çalışma alışkanlıklarına çizgi Filmlerin Etkisinin İncelenmesi (Doctoral dissertation, Marmara Üniversitesi (Turkey)).
- Çilenti, K. (1984). *Eğitim Teknolojisi Ve Öğretim*, Ankara: Özel Yayın.
- Darga, H., Öztürk, F. Z., & Öztürk, T. Çizgi Filmlerin Çocukların Dil ve Sosyal Gelişim Alanlarına Etkisine Yönelik Ebeveyn Görüşlerinin İncelenmesi. *International Primary Education Research Journal*, 5(1), 59-77.
- Doğan, A., & Göker, G. (2012). Tematik Televizyon Ve Çocuk: İlköğretim Öğrencilerinin Televizyon İzleme Alışkanlıkları. *Milli Eğitim Dergisi*, 42(194), 5-30.
- Karaca, G. (2011). 5-8 Yaş aralığındaki çocuklarda stereotip (klişe resim) kullanımı. Mehmet Akif Ersoy Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi, 3(4), 86-93.
- Kernan, M. (2007). *Play as context for early learning and development.. Dublin:NCCA*
- Merriam, S. B. (2013). Nitel araştırma: Desen ve uygulama için bir rehber (3. Baskıdan Çeviri, Çeviri Editörü: S. Turan). Ankara: Nobel Yayın Dağıtım.
- Öztürk, C., & Karayağız, G. (2007). Çocuk ve televizyon. *Anadolu Hemşirelik ve*
- Ravikiran, S. R., Baliga, B. S., Jain, A., & Kotian, M. S. (2014). Factors influencing the television viewing practices of Indian children. *The Indian Journal of Pediatrics*, 81(2), 114-119. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12098-013-1164-y>
- Rideout VJ, Vandewater EA, Wartella EA. Zero to Six: Electronic Media in the Lives of Infants, Toddlers and Preschoolers. A Kaiser Family Foundation Report, 2003.
- Samur, A. Ö., Demirhan, T. D., Soydan, S., & Önkol, L. (2014). Pepee çizgi filminin ebeveyn öğretmen ve çocuk gözüyle değerlendirilmesi/assessment of pepee cartoon from perspectives of parents teachers and children. *Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 11(26), 151-166.
- Sarıçam, H. Çizgi Film Programlarının Çocuklara Etkisi Konu-sunda Ailelerin Bilgi ve Farkındalık Düzeylerinin İncelenmesi 1...*Sağlık Bilimleri Dergisi*, 10(2), 81-85.
- Tokdemir, M., Deveci, S. E., Açıık, Y., Yağmur, M., Gülbayrak, C. ve Türkoğlu, A.R.(2009) İlköğretim Öğrencilerinin Fiziksel Şiddete Başvurma ve Fiziksel Şiddete Yaklaşımlarında Televizyon Programlarının Etkisi. *Türkiye Klinikleri Adli Tıp Dergisi*, Cilt: 6 Sayı: 2
- Yaşar Ekici, F. (2015). Çizgi filmlerin çocuklar üzerindeki etkilerine ilişkin çok boyutlu bir değerlendirme. *Türk & İslam Dünyası Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 2(5), Aralık, 70-84.
- Yener, Y., Yılmaz, M., & Mert, Ş. E. N. (2021). Çizgi filmlerde değer eğitimi: TRT Çocuk örneği. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Education Research*, 7(2), 114-128.
- Yetim, G., & Sarıçam, H. (2016). Çizgi film programlarının çocuklara etkisi konusunda ailelerin bilgi ve farkındalık düzeylerinin incelenmesi. *OPUS Uluslararası Toplum Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 6(11), 341-364.
- Yıldırım, A. ve Şimşek, H. (2011). *Sosyal bilimlerde nitel araştırma yöntemleri* (8.baskı). Ankara: Seçkin Yayıncılık.